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**Carmen Andraş, Cornel Sigmirean, Corina Teodor (eds.),
Itineraries beyond Borders of Cultures, Identities and Disciplines,
Sibiu: Editura Astra Museum, 2012**

Review by Colin Swatridge*

I have to confess, at the outset, that I am not equipped to understand spoken or written Italian. The two papers in this collection, therefore, by Mihai Teodor Nicoară and Elena Dumitru are not taken account of in this review. This is a pity to be sure since both – about aspects of life close to the border with Stalin’s Russia – have much to contribute to the theme (though, happily, Panait Istrati, featured in Dumitru’s paper, is also the subject of a paper, in English, by Dragoş Sdrobiş).

Border Studies is a fascinating, relatively new, interdisciplinary focus for thinking and research – and the title of this collection of papers needed to be long to encompass something of the variety of topics on offer here. Carmen Andraş sets the scene for us by outlining in her Introduction what ‘border studies’ are *about*: they are an interdisciplinary pursuit drawing on political, sociological, strategic, and cultural methodologies, to throw light on the psycho-geography of boundaries, of frontiers, of limits, literal and metaphorical. They are about physical mobility and affective-cognitive identity. In ‘global’ times border studies are the social science *du jour*.

This said, the idea of a the border, and of crossing (or ‘transgressing’) the border, provides us with a new tool with which to investigate and compare instances in the past of what we can now think of as border-crossings and as re-definitions of identity. The traffic of intellectuals between Romania and Italy is one such instance: Cornel Sigmirean speaks of the travels of Italians to Romania at the very time – the second half of the 18th Century – when Romanian scholars were suggesting

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that Romania's origins were to be located in Rome; in the Roman Empire; in Latinity. The Italians who journeyed to Romania acknowledged their kinship with Romanians; and the Romanians who journeyed to Italy – Samuil Micu, Gheorghe Șincai, Petru Maior, Ioan Budai-Deleanu – were delighted to discover just how much they 'recognized' in Italy, and how much they had in common with Italians. Both Italians and Romanians were in search of their origins; both found (what they might be said to have been hoping to find) in Romania: an 'unaltered type of Vulgar Latin'. It may be that Romanian philologists 'cleansed' the language of Slavic influences so that it then more closely resembled an archaic Latin; nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the delight in linguistic reciprocity was not all on the Romanians' side. It is also noteworthy that Romanians were keen to burnish the reputation of their rather misunderstood country by attaching it to a western model. Some things don't change.

Ion Codru-Drăgușanu was a traveller whose writings, Iulian Boldea points out, were 'needlessly complicated or excessively Latinized'. This 'Transylvanian Pilgrim' travelled all over Europe, fastening upon France – and on Paris in particular – as the real hub of modern civilization. 'Only one tribe in the world,' he wrote in 1844, 'asks for and deserves our esteem and gratitude. This is the French nation, which for half a century has shed its blood and uses it money only for the sake of mankind.' High praise indeed. It was Switzerland's political system, though, and especially the recognition given to the rights of each of the country's constituent nationalities, that impressed him, and that caused him to reflect upon the disadvantages suffered by his Romanian-speaking compatriots in Transylvania.

Panait Istrati was another pilgrim, but where Codru-Drăgușanu had enjoyed the bourgeois comforts of Paris and Baden-Baden, Istrati was a poor, self-taught socialist, who spent nine years in the early 1900s, wandering in search of himself, in Egypt among other countries. He returned to Romania, but, as a pacifist, he was unhappy at the prospect of Romania's becoming embroiled in war, so decamped once again to Switzerland. There he came under the influence of the French pacifist Romain Rolland, who encouraged him to write; and it was as an already accomplished writer that he returned to Romania in 1925, conscious though he was of the limiting effects of writing in what he considered to be an

‘inferior’ language. Two years in Soviet Russia (1927-29) convinced Istrati that Soviet communism was not the holy place of his pilgrimage – that, indeed, there could be no such place. He was an outsider, a humanitarian without borders, until the end.

In one of the book’s longer essays, Irina Nastasă-Matei, looks rather at the nation, Romania, than at individual Romanians: at Romania in the inter-war period, when university students were drawn either to the extreme left or to the extreme right. In part thanks to the influence of intellectuals like Mircea Eliade, Emil Cioran, A.C. Cuza, and Nae Ionescu, most politically-minded students were seduced by nationalism, rather than by international communism. The presiding ideas of the time were fascistic: anti-Semitism, eugenics, and the fear of Bolshevism. Poverty among students, high fees, the want of resources for learning, and the poor employment prospects induced too many students to look for scapegoats among generally more hard-working and successful Jewish students, for whom communism appeared to be the safer option. Anti-Semitic noises heard in Germany and Hungary were an influential, but not crucial, backdrop to a home-grown anti-Semitism represented most militantly by the League for National-Christian Defence, and the Legion of Archangel Michael. It was a temper that was by no means discouraged by the government inasmuch as – though a *numerus clausus* was not imposed by law (as it was in Hungary), *de facto* restrictions were placed on Jewish students as another war approached.

Jews were, indeed, represented in the Romanian Communist Party in numbers disproportionate to their numbers in the population at large, as Csaba Zoltán Novák points out in his paper – but then, so were Hungarians and other minorities. For Jews, communism seemed to be more promising as a guarantee against racist policies; whilst the attraction for Hungarians was that inter-war communism denied the legitimacy of borders drawn at Trianon. Both communities, before and after the Second World War, were party-card carriers rather for pragmatic than for ideological reasons; besides, both were far more likely to be of the urban working class than were Romanians.

The introverted, hate-filled nationalism of the inter-war period was a deformed version of the nation-building nationalism of the second half of

the 19th Century, howbeit the Orthodox Church stood as patron to both nationalities. Few religious divisions have as much social-political significance within a nation's borders as the division between the Catholic and Orthodox Metropolitan Andrei Şaguna, active in the 19th Century phase of nationalism, in writings about him dating from the inter-war phase. He represented for later celebrants of his life and work 'not only a piece of the Transylvanian identity-picture, but one that could lighten the connections between the church and the state'. He was, so to say, the respectable face of a church-state concordat. He synthesized the national and the confessional – a Romanian after whom streets could be fitly named. Greek Catholics had a harder job to be accepted as a national, Romanian church: whereas the Orthodox Church was identified with the emerging Romania, the Greek Catholic Church emphasized its – and the nation's – origins in the Latin church. When, therefore, Anca Sinçan explores the implications of the enforced merger of the two churches in 1948, it is to plot a play in which the two communities sought to commend their special characteristics as nation-builders. Both had to position, and re-position themselves, at first, within a Transylvania that was an outpost of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy, and subsequently in multicultural, post-1918 greater Romania. If the State co-opted the church for its purposes after 1948, the survival of the two traditions was preserved in the adoption of Romanian as the language of the liturgy, but in the Latin, not the Cyrillic script.

Part 3 of the book stretches the meaning of 'borders' still further and shows why it is worth doing so. In a close reading of Franz Liszt's *Gypsies and their Music in Hungary*, Marian Zăloagă makes the claim that Liszt says as much (and perhaps more) about himself in his celebration of gypsy music as he does about that music. Gypsies represented the free spirit, the 'other', that he was himself: they incarnated the imagined idea of the 'autonomous virtuoso musician' – which is as fitting a description as any of Franz Liszt. In trying to 'save' gypsy music for the European musical canon, though, without spoiling it by academic over-attention, he offended those, like Sámuel Brassai, who wished to play down the influence of gypsy rhythms on Magyar music. But Liszt and Brassai were defending different borders: whereas Brassai drew a borderline between gypsy and Magyar music, Liszt sought to raise a fence between authentic gypsy music

and the commercial version of it that was to be heard increasingly in the capitals of Western Europe.

Georgeta Fodor focuses on a more fundamental – and universal – border: that between men and women. She examines four journals published in Transylvania, in the latter half of the 19th Century, so see what they had to say about women's issues, and about the education of women and girls in particular. It is her principal finding that, insofar as Romanian intellectuals recognized the crucial influence of an educated mother on her family, and as educated citizens would be better equipped to confront the policies of the Pest government, so it was vital that girls should be educated to the same standard as boys, and 'in the national spirit'.

In two concise, neatly-paired papers, Simion and Maria Costea consider Romania's troubled diplomatic relations with Western Europe, before and after the Second World War. The focus of Maria Costea's paper is the claim made by Bulgaria to all or part of Dobrudja, in 1939. A highly damaging incident in Belitza, Southern Dobrudja, in which 25 Bulgarians were killed – innocent bystanders, or 'dangerous bandits' as the Romanian government insisted? – angered the Belgian Plenipotentiary Minister in Bucharest, exercised the Turks on the Bulgarian border, and unsettled diplomats on all sides in febrile times. Both Bulgaria and Romania were in a cruel dilemma as to where their loyalties lay in the event of war – and when it came to it, of course, both opted for wait-and-see neutrality. It was the abovementioned Belgian minister who kept western powers informed about the state of the armies and their battle-readiness in both countries. For their pains, it was Belgian diplomats who experienced the unhappiest effects of the neglect of diplomatic protocols on the part of the communist régime in Bucharest, in 1948. But then, the régime was neglectful of its obligations on all sides, and not least of its duty of care towards its own citizens. Belgian, British, Turkish, and American diplomats gave what aid they could to oppressed Romanians, and helped some to flee the country. In response, as Simion Costea points out, the régime accused Americans in particular of espionage, and sought to reduce the number of accredited foreign diplomats in the capital. Communist apparatchiks were simply unable to comprehend why so many foreigners were still circulating in what was – for a time – a loyal Soviet satellite.

The collection reaches completion in a paper by Mariana Neț on buildings and statues having symbolic status, erected between the wars in towns and cities close to borders; in a paper by Maria Dan on ethnic frontiers in one Transylvanian town; and in a tailpiece by Corneliu Cezar Sigmirean, that reminds us that, in cyberspace, there are no borders. After 1918, the Romanian authorities in Bucharest faced the challenge of incorporating Transylvania into the Old Kingdom, and especially, of 'Romanianizing' the border cities of Satu Mare, Oradea, Arad, and Timișoara, and the 'German' cities, Brașov and Sibiu. The obvious way of meeting this challenge was to build imposing new Orthodox cathedrals in the bigger cities, and to erect statues to Romanian notables. The building of Orthodox cathedrals was no mere political gesture, though, (in spite of the resentment among the Hungarians who were still in the majority in most urban centres): new churches were built for growing Romanian populations and for those Romanians who came to Transylvania to occupy positions in the new administration, where there had been too little provision before 1918. Still, as Marian Neț points out, these new Orthodox cathedrals need not in all cases have been quite so big.

Reghin was another 'German' town, and a closed one, as Maria Dan says, until the Habsburg conquest and the policy of social integration took effect. In 1850, Saxons represented 70% of the population of the town; sixty years later, the proportion had dropped to just over 30%, mostly in favour of Hungarians. This is not to say, though, that as old borders were breached the Saxon character of the town was altogether stifled; nor was it the case that the growing influx of Hungarians and Romanians into the town gave rise to more than trivial tensions.

To a Briton, for whom borders have always been coterminous with sea-coasts, this collection of papers was an eye-opener. In spite of what Corneliu Cezar Sigmirean – quite justifiably – has to say about the neutralization of borders as information technology unites us on screens big and small, there is much still to be said about the physical borders that there have been and that persist, and the borders that survive in the collective imagination. The Iron Curtain was, as Simion Costea says, a 'terrible frontier'; it has been pulled down – but there are still walls being built, and lines being drawn on mental maps. Researchers in border studies need not fear unemployment.

Submitted papers should be sent either by regular mail (accompanied by a CD) to:

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The Editorial Staff is looking forward to receiving your papers for times per year: **before the 1st of February, before the 1st of May, before the 1st of July and before the 1st of October.** *Studia Europaea* is thankful for the interest you show in this *Call for Papers* and hopes for a future collaboration.